

Efficient water splitting via a flexible solar-powered Hybrid thermochemical-Sulphur dioxide depolarized Electrolysis Cycle

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D3.1 SO₃ splitting catalysts shortlisting - Public

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WP3 - Materials and catalysts development

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Preface

HySelect will demonstrate the production of hydrogen (H₂) by splitting water via concentrated solar technologies (CST) with an attractive efficiency and cost, through the Hybrid Sulphur cycle (HyS). The HyS consists of two central steps: the high temperature - yet below-900°C -decomposition of sulphuric acid forming Sulphur dioxide (SO₂) and the subsequent low temperature (50-80°C) SO₂ depolarized electrolysis (SDE) of water to produce H₂. HySelect will introduce, develop and operate under real conditions a complete H₂ production chain focusing on two innovative, full scale plant prototype core devices for both steps of the HyS cycle: an allothermally heated, spatially decoupled from a centrifugal particle solar receiver, sulphuric acid decomposition-Sulphur trioxide splitting (SAD-STs) reactor and a Sulphur dioxide depolarized electrolyzer (SDE) without expensive Platinum Group Metals (PGMs). Furthermore, a heat recovery system will be integrated to exploit the temperature difference within the cycle and boost the overall process efficiency. In the course of the work, non-critical materials and catalysts will be developed, qualified and integrated into the plant scale prototype units for both the acid splitting reactor and the SDE unit. Experimental work will be accompanied by component modelling and overall process simulation and culminate with a demonstration of the complete process integrating its key units of a 750kW_{th} centrifugal particle receiver, a hot particles storage system, a 250kW_{th} SAD-STs and a 100kW_e SDE into a pilot plant. Testing for a period of at least 6 months in a large-scale solar tower, driven with smart operation and control strategies, will establish the HySelect targeted efficiency and costs. Finally, an overall process evaluation will be carried out in order to assess the technical and economic prospects of the HySelect technology, directly linked to the know-how and developments of the sulphuric acid and water electrolyzers industries.

DLR	German Aerospace Center	DE	
CERTH	Centre for Research and Technology Hellas	GR	
AALTO	Aalto University	FI	
ENEA	Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development	IT	
FENR	FEN Research GmbH	AT	
GRILLO	Grillo Werke AG	DE	

Summary

This document focuses on the synthesis and characterization of oxide-based catalytic materials employed for the SO₃ splitting (Sulphur Trioxide Splitting, STS) of the Sulphuric Acid Splitting (SAS) reaction, which is part of the overall Hybrid Sulphur (HyS) thermochemical cycle. Non-precious, metal-based formulations, primarily copper, iron, cerium and vanadium-based oxides, are employed at either medium ($\leq 650^{\circ}\text{C}$) reaction temperature (vanadium oxide-based compositions) or higher ($800\text{-}850^{\circ}\text{C}$) temperature (copper, iron and cerium oxide-based compositions). Produced materials in powder form are shaped into structures for enhanced catalytic and thermomechanical performance. For the needs of the preliminary evaluation/shortlisting, all powders are shaped into spherical or near-spherical formulations with a diameter of 1-2 mm. In all cases, the developed powders and their final formulations are characterized structurally (XRD), morphologically (SEM, Hg-porosimetry, surface area), thermally (TGA/DSC) and mechanically (crushing strength). Based on their acquired properties, catalytic performance of selected materials is evaluated, using concentrated sulphuric acid as feedstock (96.5%) for the temperatures of $800\text{-}850^{\circ}\text{C}$ and relatively dilute acid stream (25%) at temperatures $\leq 650^{\circ}\text{C}$ to simulate the intended cascaded operation of the envisaged STS reactor via tests in the range of 1-10h of on-stream exposure.

The results of the current deliverable, which serves as the preliminary shortlisting tool, are associated with the targets of the first Specific Technical Objective (SO1) which is quantified in the relative Key Performance Indicator (KPI) as follows: SO₃ conversion $\geq 75\%$ of the corresponding thermodynamic value and loss of activity $< 10\%$ for at least 3000 h on-stream exposure equivalent via accelerated tests. Based on the abovementioned targets, a selected number (up to five) of the most promising, preliminarily evaluated medium- and high-temperature catalysts will be qualified for the long-term testing that will be carried out by DLR.

The current document includes the physicochemical characterization results of all the synthesized powders (exceeding 100 different compositions), their shaping into spherical formulations as well as selected results of the evaluated catalysts (above 50 different compositions tested up to M15) predominantly focusing on high-temperature catalysts in this period. The identification of four materials that in-principle present promising results both in terms of SO₃ conversion and thermomechanical stability is already an encouraging step close to the target of “up to five promising catalysts” that will be evaluated in the long-term tests.

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1. Introduction

This document presents the development of enhanced catalytic formulations for the STS part (reaction 1b) of the SAS step of the Hybrid Sulphur (HyS) thermochemical cycle that are investigated within Work Package 3 (Materials and catalysts development). The HyS cycle consists of two main reactions (Table 1); the first is the SAS reaction (Reaction 1) that includes the decomposition of sulphuric acid (H₂SO₄) to sulphur dioxide (SO₂) and oxygen (O₂) through reactions set 1a (non-catalytic) and 1b (catalytic), and the second is the electrolysis step (Reaction 2) in which sulphur dioxide and water form sulphurous acid (H₂SO₃) that is used to depolarize the anode and sulphuric acid is produced yielding two protons and two electrons. Then, at the cathode, the protons and electrons are recombined forming H₂.

Table 1: Chemical reactions of the HyS thermochemical cycle.

HyS Reactions		T _{reac} (°C)
Sulphuric acid splitting (SAS)	1 H ₂ SO ₄ (g) → H ₂ O(g) + SO ₂ (g) + ½ O ₂ (g)	
Sulphuric acid dissociation (SAD)	1a H ₂ SO ₄ (g) → H ₂ O(g) + SO ₃ (g)	450-500
Sulphur trioxide splitting (STS)	1b SO ₃ (g) → SO ₂ (g) + ½ O ₂ (g)	650-950
Electrolysis	2 2 H ₂ O + SO ₂ → H ₂ SO ₄ + H ₂ (g)	
Anode	SO ₂ + 2 H ₂ O → H ₂ SO ₄ + 2 H ⁺ + 2 e ⁻	50
Cathode	2 H ⁺ + 2 e ⁻ → H ₂	

Task 3.1 “Enhanced sulphuric acid splitting catalyst formulations”, based on extensive past experience of partners on materials development regarding both medium and high reaction temperatures, focuses on the synthesis of non-precious, metal-based formulations that will target at both medium (≤650°C) and high reaction temperatures (800-850°C) [1], [2] with the main target being to meet the requirements of SO1 in terms of SO₃ conversion exceeding 75% of the corresponding thermodynamic value. The aim of the two different temperature ranges that will be studied is to simulate the cascaded operation envisaged for the scale-up STS reactor that will be designed and constructed within the framework of the Project.

Several metal oxides have been considered as active catalysts for the splitting of sulphur trioxide at temperatures ranging from 600 to 950°C [3]. Noble metal catalysts are highly active for SO₃ splitting reactions, however, non-noble compositions should be developed with respect to economic viability and resources sustainability [4]. Additionally, the development of active and economically viable catalysts for SO₃ splitting at ≤650°C is also important. Vanadium (V) oxides, mixed with Copper (Cu) or Cerium (Ce) have been reported to be catalytically active for SO₃ splitting at moderate reaction temperatures; supported Cu and Ce-based vanadates appear to be active at 600-650°C [5], [6], [7]. At higher reaction temperatures iron oxide (Fe₂O₃) and copper oxide (CuO) are considered active components that in combination with Si or Al on a suitable substrate can constitute a promising catalyst exhibiting satisfactory catalytic activity and thermomechanical stability [3], [8], [9].

2. Medium-temperature material synthesis and characterization

Relying on literature review and past experience, a series of single and mixed metal oxide catalysts have been prepared, based on Vanadium (V), Cerium (Ce) and Copper (Cu). Various simple synthesis methods have been employed, involving thermal decomposition, dissolution-evaporation-precipitation steps, and dry mixing.

Single or mixed oxides have been supported on substrates, such as aluminum oxide (Al₂O₃), silicon dioxide (SiO₂) and kaolinite (Al₂Si₂O₅(OH)₄). Kaolinite is a clay mineral and constitutes an abundant, cost-effective and attrition resistant ceramic binding agent. All supported samples have been structured into spherical particles to enhance resilience to chemically “harsh” reaction conditions combined with minimal pressure drop.

Both supported and unsupported samples have been physicochemically characterized employing the following selected methods:

- Specific surface area measurements (BET) by liquid N₂ adsorption and determination of porous microstructure characteristics.
- Porosity and pore size distribution measurements via Hg-porosimetry.
- Phase composition determination via X-ray Diffraction (XRD).
- Structural observation and elemental micro-analysis via Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) & Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy (EDS) respectively.
- Mass change measurements during heating via Thermogravimetric Analysis/ Differential Scanning Calorimetry (TGA/DSC).
- Crushing strength (CS) of structured particles upon calcination (fresh) and after testing in reaction environment (used).

2.1. Single metal oxides

Single metal oxides have been synthesized via thermal decomposition (**TD**) and dissolution-precipitation-precipitation (**DEP**) techniques. Ammonium metavanadate (NH₄VO₃) has been employed as the precursor for vanadium species, cerium nitrate (Ce(NO₃)₃·6H₂O) for cerium species and copper nitrate (Cu(NO₃)₂·2.5H₂O) for copper species. Table 2 presents synthesized single metal oxides, along with the precursor employed, as well as the commercial material. Prepared single copper and cerium oxides are presented into the Section 3 “High-temperature material synthesis and characterization” of the current document, as they will be used for high temperature reactions.

Table 2: Catalytic formulations – Unsupported single oxides.

Sample No.	Synthesized Oxides	Metal Precursors	Synthesis Method
1	V ₂ O ₅	NH ₄ VO ₃	TD
2	V ₂ O ₅	NH ₄ VO ₃	DEP
3	V ₂ O ₅	-	Commercial

TD refers to the calcination of a precursor (i.e., NH₄VO₃) at 600°C, for 4h, under air flow (heating rate: 5°C/min). DEP method includes the dissolution of a precursor in water, and then the addition of a support material (when applied), under magnetic stirring for 2h, followed by solvent evaporation and overnight drying (120°C). The obtained powder is sintered up to 600°C, for 4h, under air flow (heating rate: 5°C/min).

Silicon dioxide, aluminum oxide and kaolinite have been employed as support materials, in a precursor/support material ratio of 15/85 wt%. Dry mixing (**DM**) involves dry mixing for 1h of the powder of an oxide catalyst that has either been synthesized or commercially procured, with that of a support. Selected samples have been calcined in order to identify the produced phases. Table 3 presents synthesized supported oxides, prepared using DEP steps, as well as via DM of commercial and synthesized oxides on each support.

Table 3: Catalytic formulations – Supported single oxides.

Sample No.	Supported Oxides	Metal Precursors	Synthesis Method
4	Kaolinite	-	Commercial
5	V ₂ O ₅ /Kaolinite	NH ₄ VO ₃	DEP
6	V ₂ O ₅ /Kaolinite	V ₂ O ₅ [#3]	DM
7	V ₂ O ₅ /Kaolinite	V ₂ O ₅ [#1]	DM
8	V ₂ O ₅ /Kaolinite	V ₂ O ₅ [#2]	DM
9	SiO ₂	-	Commercial
10	V ₂ O ₅ /SiO ₂	NH ₄ VO ₃	DEP
11	V ₂ O ₅ /SiO ₂	V ₂ O ₅ [#3]	DM
12	V ₂ O ₅ /SiO ₂	V ₂ O ₅ [#1]	DM
13	V ₂ O ₅ /SiO ₂	V ₂ O ₅ [#2]	DM
14	Al ₂ O ₃	-	Commercial
15	V ₂ O ₅ /Al ₂ O ₃	NH ₄ VO ₃	DEP
16	V ₂ O ₅ /Al ₂ O ₃	V ₂ O ₅ [#3]	DM
17	V ₂ O ₅ /Al ₂ O ₃	V ₂ O ₅ [#1]	DM
18	V ₂ O ₅ /Al ₂ O ₃	V ₂ O ₅ [#2]	DM

Characterization of unsupported samples with respect to BET surface area, porous characteristics, and crystallite size (calculated from XRD) are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Characterization – Unsupported single oxides

Sample No./ Description	BET Surface Area (m ² /g)	Pore Volume (cm ³ /g)	Pore Size (nm)	Phase Composition	Crystallite Size (nm)
1 [V ₂ O ₅]	2.5	0.035	102.0	V ₂ O ₅	57.0
2 [V ₂ O ₅]	2.6	0.036	90.6	V ₂ O ₅	79.8
3 [V ₂ O ₅]	4.6	0.055	60.9	V ₂ O ₅	53.2

Figure 1: X-Ray diffractograms of synthesized and commercial vanadium oxides.

Figure 1 presents the X-Ray diffractograms of unsupported V₂O₅ oxides that have either been synthesized or commercially procured. Synthesized samples are similar to the commercial one, while the vanadium oxide prepared via the DEP method showed the highest crystallite size. SEM micrographs also show that there are no significant differences among the three different vanadium oxides. However, DEP results in the formation of relatively smaller particles.

Figure 2: SEM micrographs of vanadium oxides (a) V₂O₅ [#1], (b) V₂O₅ [#2], and (c) V₂O₅ [#3]

Characterization of supported samples with respect to BET surface area, porous characteristics and phase composition (by X-Ray Diffraction) is presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Characterization – Supported single oxides.

Sample No./ Description	BET Surface Area (m ² /g)	Pore Volume (cm ³ /g)	Pore Size (nm)	Phase Composition (XRD)
4 [Kaolinite]	17.3	0.123	16.5	Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
5 [V ₂ O ₅ /Kaolinite]	12.7	0.008	-	V ₂ O ₅ , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
6 [V ₂ O ₅ /Kaolinite]	14.3	0.089	26.4	V ₂ O ₅ , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
7 [V ₂ O ₅ /Kaolinite]	15.1	0.095	-	V ₂ O ₅ , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
8 [V ₂ O ₅ /Kaolinite]	11.8	0.073	-	V ₂ O ₅ , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
9 [SiO ₂]	5.0	0.045	52.5	SiO ₂
10 [V ₂ O ₅ /SiO ₂]	4.1	0.039	53.5	V ₂ O ₅ , SiO ₂
11 [V ₂ O ₅ /SiO ₂]	5.1	0.048	45.5	V ₂ O ₅ , SiO ₂

12 [V ₂ O ₅ /SiO ₂]	4.4	0.042	44.2	V ₂ O ₅ , SiO ₂
13 [V ₂ O ₅ /SiO ₂]	4.4	0.043	47.3	V ₂ O ₅ , SiO ₂
14 [Al ₂ O ₃]	0.6	0.016	98.7	Al ₂ O ₃ , (Al ₂ O ₃) ₁₁ (H ₂ O) _{1.79} , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
15 [V ₂ O ₅ /Al ₂ O ₃]	1.0	0.022	110.8	Al ₂ O ₃ , V ₂ O ₅ , (Al ₂ O ₃) ₁₁ (H ₂ O) _{1.79} , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
16 [V ₂ O ₅ /Al ₂ O ₃]	1.3	0.023	107.8	Al ₂ O ₃ , V ₂ O ₅ , (Al ₂ O ₃) ₁₁ (H ₂ O) _{1.79} , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
17 [V ₂ O ₅ /Al ₂ O ₃]	0.8	0.019	123.7	Al ₂ O ₃ , V ₂ O ₅ , (Al ₂ O ₃) ₁₁ (H ₂ O) _{1.79} , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
18 [V ₂ O ₅ /Al ₂ O ₃]	1.0	0.019	120.8	Al ₂ O ₃ , V ₂ O ₅ , (Al ₂ O ₃) ₁₁ (H ₂ O) _{1.79} , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄

Figure 3 presents the SEM images of all employed supports, while Figures 4-6 present supported vanadium oxides on kaolinite, SiO₂, and Al₂O₃. In all cases, no significant morphological differences have been observed.

Figure 3: SEM micrographs of supports (a) Kaolinite [#6], (b) SiO₂ [#9], and (c) Al₂O₃ [#14]

Figure 4: SEM micrographs of (a) V₂O₅/Kaolinite [#5], (b) V₂O₅/Kaolinite [#6], (c) V₂O₅/Kaolinite [#7], and (d) V₂O₅/Kaolinite [#8]

Figure 5: SEM micrographs of (a) V₂O₅/SiO₂ [#10], (b) V₂O₅/SiO₂ [#11], (c) V₂O₅/SiO₂ [#12], and (d) V₂O₅/SiO₂ [#13]

Figure 6: SEM micrographs of (a) V₂O₅/Al₂O₃ [#15], and (b) V₂O₅/Al₂O₃ [#16]

2.2. Mixed metal oxides

Mixed oxides of Vanadium (V), Copper (Cu) and Cerium (Ce) have been prepared using DEP steps or DM synthesis methods (described in the previous sub-section), in various metal molar ratios (i.e., 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 or 2:1), as indicated in parentheses for each sample in the following tables. Table 6 presents all synthesized mixed metal oxides, along with the precursors or oxides that have been used for each sample. A commercial BiVO₄ grade supplied by the industrial partner Grillo with, in-principle, promising properties and –quite importantly– no toxicity, which is the case for most V-based compositions, is also included.

Table 6: Catalytic formulations – Unsupported mixed oxides

Sample No.	Synthesized Oxides	Metal Precursors	Synthesis Method
19	BiVO ₄	-	Commercial
20	Ce-V (1:1)	Ce(NO ₃) ₃ ·6H ₂ O & NH ₄ VO ₃	DEP
21	Ce-V (1:1)	CeO ₂ [#55] & V ₂ O ₅ [#3]	DM
22	Ce-V (1:2)	Ce(NO ₃) ₃ ·6H ₂ O & NH ₄ VO ₃	DEP
23	Ce-V (1:2)	CeO ₂ [#55] & V ₂ O ₅ [#3]	DM
24	Cu-V (1:1)	Cu(NO ₃) ₂ ·2.5H ₂ O & NH ₄ VO ₃	DEP
25	Cu-V (1:1)	CuO [#57] & V ₂ O ₅ [#3]	DM
26	Cu-V (1:2)	Cu(NO ₃) ₂ ·2.5H ₂ O & NH ₄ VO ₃	DEP
27	Cu-V (1:2)	CuO [#57] & V ₂ O ₅ [#3]	DM
28	Cu-V (1:3)	Cu(NO ₃) ₂ ·2.5H ₂ O & NH ₄ VO ₃	DEP
29	Cu-V (2:1)	Cu(NO ₃) ₂ ·2.5H ₂ O & NH ₄ VO ₃	DEP

As with single oxides, SiO₂, Al₂O₃ and kaolinite have been employed as substrates, in a precursor/support material ratio of 15/85 wt%, using the synthesis methods described above. Table 7 presents synthesized supported oxides, prepared using DEP or DM.

Table 7: Catalytic formulations – Supported mixed oxides.

Sample No.	Supported Oxides	Metal Precursors	Synthesis Method
30	BiVO ₄ /Kaolinite	BiVO ₄ [#30]	DM
31	Ce-V (1:1)/Kaolinite	Ce(NO ₃) ₃ ·6H ₂ O & NH ₄ VO ₃	DEP
32	Ce-V (1:2)/Kaolinite	Ce(NO ₃) ₃ ·6H ₂ O & NH ₄ VO ₃	DEP
33	Cu-V (1:1)/Kaolinite	Cu(NO ₃) ₂ ·2.5H ₂ O & NH ₄ VO ₃	DEP
34	Cu-V (1:2)/Kaolinite	Cu(NO ₃) ₂ ·2.5H ₂ O & NH ₄ VO ₃	DEP
35	Cu-V (2:1)/Kaolinite	Cu(NO ₃) ₂ ·2.5H ₂ O & NH ₄ VO ₃	DEP
36	Ce-V (1:1)/SiO ₂	Ce(NO ₃) ₃ ·6H ₂ O & NH ₄ VO ₃	DEP
37	Ce-V (1:2)/SiO ₂	Ce(NO ₃) ₃ ·6H ₂ O & NH ₄ VO ₃	DEP
38	Cu-V (1:1)/SiO ₂	Cu(NO ₃) ₂ ·2.5H ₂ O & NH ₄ VO ₃	DEP
39	Cu-V (1:2)/SiO ₂	Cu(NO ₃) ₂ ·2.5H ₂ O & NH ₄ VO ₃	DEP
40	Cu-V (2:1)/SiO ₂	Cu(NO ₃) ₂ ·2.5H ₂ O & NH ₄ VO ₃	DEP

Table 8 presents BET surface area and porous characteristics of mixed unsupported oxides, as well as their composition based on XRD. Main XRD peaks for each sample are indicated in the text in bold, including the main catalytically active phases of CeVO₄, Cu₂V₂O₇ and CuV₂O₆ as also identified in the relative literature.

Table 8: Characterization – Unsupported mixed oxides.

Sample No./ Description	BET Surface Area (m ² /g)	Pore Volume (cm ³ /g)	Pore Size (nm)	Phase Composition (XRD)
19 [BiVO ₄]	0.3	0.001	-	BiVO₄ , Bi ₄ V ₂ O ₁₁ , V ₂ O ₅ , Bi ₂ O ₃
20 [Ce-V (1:1)]	6.9	0.075	58.2	CeVO₄ , CeO ₂ , V ₂ O ₅
21 [Ce-V (1:1)]	7.3	0.076	46.7	CeO ₂ , V ₂ O ₅
22 [Ce-V (1:2)]	2.2	0.018	78.8	CeVO₄ , V ₂ O ₅
23 [Ce-V (1:2)]	6.5	0.083	53.9	CeO ₂ , V ₂ O ₅
24 [Cu-V (1:1)]	1.7	0.007	271.0	Cu₂V₂O₇ , CuV ₂ O ₆ , Cu ₃ (VO ₄) ₂
25 [Cu-V (1:1)]	2.6	0.026	65.1	CuO, V ₂ O ₅
26 [Cu-V (1:2)]	1.4	0.009	119.0	CuV₂O₆ , Cu ₂ V ₂ O ₇ , V ₂ O ₅
27 [Cu-V (1:2)]	4.3	0.061	90.5	CuO, V ₂ O ₅
28 [Cu-V (1:3)]	1.7	0.036	172.2	CuV₂O₆ , V ₂ O ₅
29 [Cu-V (2:1)]	1.3	0.008	124.1	CuV₂O₆ , Cu ₂ V ₂ O ₇ , V ₂ O ₅

Different metal ratios have been selected in order to evaluate the formation of mixed oxides (*i.e.*, CeVO₄, Cu₂V₂O₇, CuV₂O₆), as they have been reported to be catalytically active for SO₃ splitting. The main phase detected for all samples produced via dissolution-evaporation-precipitation, followed by calcination, were mixed (binary) oxides. DM-prepared samples confirmed the presence of solely single oxides. Figures 7 & 8 present the X-ray diffractograms of synthesized species that support the above. Figure 9 shows selected, indicative SEM micrographs of Ce-V (1:1) [#20] and Ce-V (1:2) [#22] samples.

Figure 7: X-Ray diffractograms of synthesized Cu-V oxides via DEP

Figure 8: X-Ray diffractograms of synthesized Ce-V oxides via DEP

Figure 9: SEM micrographs of (a) Ce-V (1:1) [#20] and (b) Ce-V (1:2) [#22]

Upon calcination of DM samples, following the same as in DEP calcination protocol, mixed phases were formed, while single oxides were also present. A comparison of these samples, prior to and post calcination, is presented in Figure 10, for the Ce-V oxides, where the letter C indicates the calcined samples. While the samples Ce-V (1:1) [#21] and Ce-V (1:2) [#23] only contained CeO₂ and V₂O₅, CeVO₄ was also detected along with the single oxides, even though in both cases the primary peak was attributed to CeO₂.

Figure 10: X-Ray diffractograms of synthesized cerium-vanadium oxides via DM.

Figure 11 presents Cu-V oxides that have been synthesized via DM, prior to and post calcination. Correspondingly with the Ce-V oxides, Cu-V (1:1) [#25] and Cu-V (1:2) [#27] contained CuO and V₂O₅, while, upon calcination CuV₂O₆ and Cu₂V₂O₇ were also detected, despite the fact that the primary peak was that of V₂O₅.

Figure 11: X-Ray diffractograms of synthesized copper-vanadium oxides via DM.

Table 9 presents BET surface area and porous characteristics of mixed supported oxides, as well as their composition based on X-ray diffraction (XRD).

Table 9: Characterization – Supported mixed oxides

Sample No./ Description	BET Surface Area (m ² /g)	Pore Volume (cm ³ /g)	Pore Size (nm)	Phase Composition (XRD)
30 [BiVO ₄ /Kaolinite]	14.4	0.121	33.8	BiVO ₄ , SiO ₂ , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
31 [Ce-V (1:1)/Kaolinite]	18.6	0.120	25.6	CeVO ₄ , CeO ₂ , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
32 [Ce-V (1:2)/Kaolinite]	15.6	0.109	29.1	CeVO ₄ , V ₂ O ₅ , CeO ₂ , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
33 [Cu-V (1:1)/Kaolinite]	13.5	0.074	26.0	Cu ₂ V ₂ O ₇ , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
34 [Cu-V (1:2)/Kaolinite]	13.6	0.070	25.2	Cu ₂ V ₂ O ₇ , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
35 [Cu-V (2:1)/Kaolinite]	13.5	0.084	25.9	Cu ₂ V ₂ O ₇ , Cu ₁₁ O ₂ (VO ₄) ₆ , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
36 [Ce-V (1:1)/ SiO ₂]	5.6	0.056	46.3	CeVO ₄ , CeO ₂ , V ₂ O ₅ , SiO ₂
37 [Ce-V (1:2)/ SiO ₂]	4.6	0.051	50.4	CeVO ₄ , CeO ₂ , V ₂ O ₅ , SiO ₂
38 [Cu-V (1:1)/ SiO ₂]	4.1	0.053	63.3	Cu ₂ V ₂ O ₇ , CuV ₂ O ₆ , SiO ₂
39 [Cu-V (1:2)/ SiO ₂]	3.7	0.035	55.9	Cu ₂ V ₂ O ₇ , CuV ₂ O ₆ , V ₂ O ₅ , SiO ₂
40 [Cu-V (2:1)/ SiO ₂]	5.3	0.022	20.9	Cu ₂ V ₂ O ₇ , Cu ₁₁ O ₂ (VO ₄) ₆ , Cu ₅ V ₂ O ₁₀ , CuO, SiO ₂

SEM images of selected samples with 1:1 molar ratio, supported on kaolinite or SiO₂, are presented in Figure 12.

Figure 12: SEM micrographs of (a) Ce-V (1:1)/Kaolinite [#31], (b) Cu-V (1:1)/Kaolinite [#33], (c) Ce-V (1:1)/SiO₂ [#36], and (d) Cu-V (1:1)/SiO₂ [#38]

2.3. Structured materials

Supported synthesized materials described above, have been structured in spherical specimens (granules) of 1-2 mm diameter, following a simplified preparation route that minimizes the intermediate production steps, and thus the overall effort, duration and energy required by the process. Shaping is a necessary step because in the final envisaged STS reactor the chosen catalyst will be in structured and not in fine powder form. Structured particles constitute a formulation which is representative to the one of the STS reactor catalyst (honeycombs, foams or particles) and is a case that does not require material quantities at the kg-scale, which is not realistic in the frame of a shortlisting phase that involves a very large number of compositions' synthesis and screening.

Table 10 presents selected medium-temperature materials that were structured in spherical particles together with their measured crushing strength (CS) after their calcination.

Table 10: Structured materials – Supported single and mixed oxides

Sample No.	Description	Synthesis Method	CS (N)
41	V ₂ O ₅ /Kaolinite [#5]	DEP	2.9
42	V ₂ O ₅ /Kaolinite [#6]	DM	8.6
43	V ₂ O ₅ /Kaolinite [#7]	DM	6.9
44	V ₂ O ₅ /Kaolinite [#8]	DM	6.7
45	V ₂ O ₅ /SiO ₂ [#10]	DEP	1.9
46	V ₂ O ₅ /SiO ₂ [#11]	DM	2.7
47	V ₂ O ₅ /SiO ₂ [#12]	DM	4.0

48	V ₂ O ₅ /SiO ₂ [#13]	DM	2.6
49	V ₂ O ₅ /Al ₂ O ₃ [#16]	DM	5.1
50	Ce-V (1:1)/Kaolinite [#31]	DEP	0.6
51	Ce-V (1:2)/Kaolinite [#32]	DEP	1.5
52	Cu-V (1:1)/Kaolinite [#33]	DEP	1.0
53	Cu-V (1:2)/Kaolinite [#34]	DEP	0.9

The particle preparation (spheronization) route includes the following steps:

- Addition of suitable (initially identified by trial and error) quantity of moisture (water and polyvinyl acetate, PVA as a binder when deemed necessary) depending on the sample **Error! Reference source not found.**)
- Slow-drying of shaped particles in ambient air
- Calcination of the particles at least 50°C above the reaction temperature to ensure the phase composition is thermally stabilized prior to the on-stream exposure (e.g. for V-rich compositions at 700°C, at Fe-, Ce-, Cu- rich at >950°C), under air flow, for 4h (heating rate: 5°C/min).

Figure 13: Lab-scale multi-bowl spheronizer (equipment acquired in the framework of the Project)

Figure 14: Spherical particles of V₂O₅/Kaolinite (15/85 wt%) samples (a) V₂O₅/Kaolinite [#6], (b) V₂O₅/Kaolinite [#7], and (c) V₂O₅/Kaolinite [#8]

Figure 15: Spherical particles of samples (a) V₂O₅/SiO₂ (15/85 wt%) [#11] (a) V₂O₅/Kaolinite [#6], (b) Ce-V (1:2)/ SiO₂ [#37], and (c) BiVO₄/Kaolinite [#30]

3. High-temperature catalysts: Synthesis and characterization

Based on literature review and past experience on SO₃ splitting materials, a series of single and mixed metal oxide catalysts have been prepared using CeO₂, CuO and Fe₂O₃. The employed simplified synthesis methods include **DEP** or dissolution-precipitation (**DP**) steps and **DM**.

As in Section 2 of the current deliverable, single or mixed oxides have been supported on the same support materials, namely Al₂O₃, SiO₂ and Al₂Si₂O₅(OH)₄ (kaolinite), whereas the same physicochemical characterization path has been followed.

3.1. Single metal oxides

Single metal oxides have been synthesized via DEP. Iron nitrate (Fe(NO₃)₃·9H₂O) has been employed as the precursor for iron species, aluminum nitrate (Al(NO₃)₃·9H₂O) for aluminum species, cerium nitrate (Ce(NO₃)₃·6H₂O) for cerium species and copper nitrate (Cu(NO₃)₂·2.5H₂O) for copper species. Table 11 presents all synthesized single metal oxides, along with the precursors employed, as well as commercial oxides for reference purposes.

Table 11: Catalytic formulations – Unsupported single oxides.

Sample No.	Synthesized Oxides	Metal Precursors	Synthesis Method
54	CeO ₂	Ce(NO ₃) ₃ ·6H ₂ O	DEP
55	CeO ₂	-	Commercial
56	CuO	Cu(NO ₃) ₂ ·2.5H ₂ O	DEP
57	CuO	-	Commercial
58	Fe ₂ O ₃	Fe(NO ₃) ₃ ·9H ₂ O	DP
59	Fe ₂ O ₃	-	Commercial

Table 12 presents synthesized supported oxides, prepared using the DEP method, as well as via DM of commercial and synthesized oxides on each support.

Table 12: Catalytic formulations – Supported single oxides.

Sample No.	Supported Oxides	Metal Precursors	Synthesis Method
60	CeO ₂ /Kaolinite	Ce(NO ₃) ₃ ·6H ₂ O	DEP
61	CeO ₂ /Kaolinite	CeO ₂ [#55]	DM
62	CeO ₂ /Kaolinite	CeO ₂ [#54]	DM
63	CeO ₂ /SiO ₂	Ce(NO ₃) ₃ ·6H ₂ O	DEP
64	CeO ₂ /SiO ₂	CeO ₂ [#55]	DM
65	CeO ₂ /SiO ₂	CeO ₂ [#54]	DM
66	CeO ₂ /Al ₂ O ₃	Ce(NO ₃) ₃ ·6H ₂ O	DEP

67	CeO ₂ /Al ₂ O ₃	CeO ₂ [#55]	DM
68	CeO ₂ /Al ₂ O ₃	CeO ₂ [#54]	DM
69	CuO/Kaolinite	Cu(NO ₃) ₂ .2.5H ₂ O	DEP
70	CuO/Kaolinite	CuO [#57]	DM
71	CuO/Kaolinite	CuO [#56]	DM
72	CuO/SiO ₂	Cu(NO ₃) ₂ .2.5H ₂ O	DEP
73	CuO/SiO ₂	CuO [#57]	DM
74	CuO/SiO ₂	CuO [#56]	DM
75	CuO/Al ₂ O ₃	Cu(NO ₃) ₂ .2.5H ₂ O	DEP
76	CuO/Al ₂ O ₃	CuO [#57]	DM
77	CuO/Al ₂ O ₃	CuO [#56]	DM
78	Fe ₂ O ₃ /Kaolinite	Fe(NO ₃) ₃ .9H ₂ O	DP
79	Fe ₂ O ₃ /Kaolinite	Fe ₂ O ₃ [#59]	DM
80	Fe ₂ O ₃ /Kaolinite	Fe ₂ O ₃ [#58]	DM
81	Fe ₂ O ₃ /SiO ₂	Fe(NO ₃) ₃ .9H ₂ O	DP
82	Fe ₂ O ₃ /SiO ₂	Fe ₂ O ₃ [#59]	DM
83	Fe ₂ O ₃ /SiO ₂	Fe ₂ O ₃ [#58]	DM
84	Fe ₂ O ₃ /Al ₂ O ₃	Fe(NO ₃) ₃ .9H ₂ O	DP
85	Fe ₂ O ₃ /Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃ [#59]	DM
86	Fe ₂ O ₃ /Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃ [#58]	DM

Characterization of samples with respect to BET surface area, porous characteristics, and crystallite size (calculated from X-ray diffractograms) are presented in Table 13.

Table 13: Characterization – Unsupported single oxides.

Sample No./ Description	BET Surface Area (m ² /g)	Pore Volume (cm ³ /g)	Pore Size (nm)	Phase Composition	Crystallite Size (nm)
54 [CeO ₂]	7.81	0.106	46.6	CeO ₂	74.51
55 [CeO ₂]	8.60	0.061	32.6	CeO ₂	68.30
56 [CuO]	0.35	0.006	195.3	CuO	27.49
57 [CuO]	3.10	0.022	56.9	CuO	7.18
58 [Fe ₂ O ₃]	11.32	0.131	28.3	Fe ₂ O ₃	81.97
59 [Fe ₂ O ₃]	3.65	0.002	-	Fe ₂ O ₃	81.49

Figures 16, 18 and 20 present the X-ray diffractograms of unsupported in-house and commercial cerium oxides, while Figures 17, 19 and 21 the SEM images of the corresponding samples.

Figure 16: X-Ray diffractograms of synthesized and commercial cerium oxides

Figure 17: SEM micrographs of cerium oxides (a) CeO₂ [#54], and (b) CeO₂ [#55]

Figure 18: X-Ray diffractograms of synthesized and commercial copper oxides

Figure 19: SEM micrographs of copper oxides (a) CuO [#56], and (b) CuO [#57]

Figure 20: X-Ray diffractograms of synthesized and commercial iron oxides

Figure 21: SEM micrographs of iron oxides (a) Fe₂O₃ [#58], and (b) Fe₂O₃ [#59]

Table 14: Characterization – Supported single oxides.

Sample No./ Description	BET surface area (m ² /g)	Pore volume (cm ³ /g)	Pore size (nm)	Phase composition (XRD)
60 [CeO ₂ /Kaolinite]	26.5	0.017	-	CeO ₂ , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
61 [CeO ₂ /Kaolinite]	15.2	0.136	36.6	CeO ₂ , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
62 [CeO ₂ /Kaolinite]	23.9	0.015	-	CeO ₂ , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
63 [CeO ₂ /SiO ₂]	4.1	0.039	53.5	CeO ₂ , SiO ₂
64 [CeO ₂ /SiO ₂]	5.7	0.051	41.6	CeO ₂ , SiO ₂
65 [CeO ₂ /SiO ₂]	13.4	0.055	58.9	CeO ₂ , SiO ₂
66 [CeO ₂ /Al ₂ O ₃]	6.6	0.049	26.3	CeO ₂ , Al ₂ O ₃ , (Al ₂ O ₃) ₁₁ (H ₂ O) _{1.79}
67 [CeO ₂ /Al ₂ O ₃]	<i>pending</i>	<i>pending</i>	<i>pending</i>	CeO ₂ , Al ₂ O ₃ , (Al ₂ O ₃) ₁₁ (H ₂ O) _{1.79} , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
68 [CeO ₂ /Al ₂ O ₃]	7.9	0.048	19.7	CeO ₂ , Al ₂ O ₃ , (Al ₂ O ₃) ₁₁ (H ₂ O) _{1.79} , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
69 [CuO/Kaolinite]	16.1	0.011	-	CuO, Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
70 [CuO/Kaolinite]	14.6	0.163	47.7	CuO, Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
71 [CuO/Kaolinite]	14.8	0.009	-	CuO, Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
72 [CuO/SiO ₂]	5.2	0.044	42.3	CuO, SiO ₂
73 [CuO/SiO ₂]	4.8	0.047	47.1	CuO, SiO ₂
74 [CuO/SiO ₂]	4.2	0.055	58.9	CuO, SiO ₂
75 [CuO/Al ₂ O ₃]	0.9	0.023	86.4	CuO, Al ₂ O ₃ , (Al ₂ O ₃) ₁₁ (H ₂ O) _{1.79} , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
76 [CuO/Al ₂ O ₃]	1.1	0.025	115.4	CuO, Al ₂ O ₃ , (Al ₂ O ₃) ₁₁ (H ₂ O) _{1.79} , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
77 [CuO/Al ₂ O ₃]	0.7	0.017	106.1	CuO, Al ₂ O ₃ , (Al ₂ O ₃) ₁₁ (H ₂ O) _{1.79} , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
78 [Fe ₂ O ₃ /Kaolinite]	24.4	0.154	22.2	Fe ₂ O ₃ , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
79 [Fe ₂ O ₃ /Kaolinite]	14.7	0.179	30.8	Fe ₂ O ₃ , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
80 [Fe ₂ O ₃ /Kaolinite]	14.7	0.138	40.6	Fe ₂ O ₃ , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
81 [Fe ₂ O ₃ /SiO ₂]	17.7	0.097	16.7	Fe ₂ O ₃ , SiO ₂
82 [Fe ₂ O ₃ /SiO ₂]	4.8	0.047	47.7	Fe ₂ O ₃ , SiO ₂
83 [Fe ₂ O ₃ /SiO ₂]	<i>pending</i>	<i>pending</i>	<i>pending</i>	Fe ₂ O ₃ , SiO ₂
84 [Fe ₂ O ₃ /Al ₂ O ₃]	10.0	0.052	16.3	Fe ₂ O ₃ , Al ₂ O ₃ , (Al ₂ O ₃) ₁₁ (H ₂ O) _{1.79} , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
85 [Fe ₂ O ₃ /Al ₂ O ₃]	1.1	0.019	99.5	Fe ₂ O ₃ , Al ₂ O ₃ , (Al ₂ O ₃) ₁₁ (H ₂ O) _{1.79} , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄
86 [Fe ₂ O ₃ /Al ₂ O ₃]	<i>pending</i>	<i>pending</i>	<i>pending</i>	Fe ₂ O ₃ , Al ₂ O ₃ , (Al ₂ O ₃) ₁₁ (H ₂ O) _{1.79} , Al ₂ (Si ₂ O ₅)(OH) ₄

3.2. Mixed metal oxides

Mixed metal oxides of Fe and Cu have been prepared using the DEP and DP methods or DM (described in the previous sub-section), in various metal molar ratios, as indicated in parentheses for each sample in the following tables. Table 15 presents all synthesized mixed metal oxides, while Figures 22 - 25 include the X-Ray diffractograms and Figure 26 indicative SEM micrographs of selected samples.

Table 15: Catalytic formulations – mixed oxides.

Sample No.	Synthesized Oxides	Precursors/Oxides	Synthesis Method
87	Fe-Cu (1:1)	Fe(NO ₃) ₃ .9H ₂ O & Cu(NO ₃) ₂ .2.5H ₂ O	DP
88	Fe-Cu (1:1)	Fe ₂ O ₃ [#59] & CuO [#57]	DM
89	Fe-Cu (2:1)	Fe(NO ₃) ₃ .9H ₂ O & Cu(NO ₃) ₂ .2.5H ₂ O	DP
90	Fe-Cu (2:1)	Fe ₂ O ₃ [#59] & CuO [#57]	DM
91	Cu-Al (1:1)	Cu(NO ₃) ₂ .2.5H ₂ O & Al(NO ₃) ₃ .9H ₂ O	DEP
92	Cu-Al (1:1)	CuO [#57] & Al ₂ O ₃ [#14]	DM
93	Cu-Al (1:2)	Cu(NO ₃) ₂ .2.5H ₂ O & Al(NO ₃) ₃ .9H ₂ O	DEP
94	Cu-Al (1:2)	CuO [#57] & Al ₂ O ₃ [#14]	DM
95	Fe-Al (1:1)	Fe(NO ₃) ₃ .9H ₂ O & Al(NO ₃) ₃ .9H ₂ O	DEP
96	Fe-Al (1:1)	Fe ₂ O ₃ [#59] & Al ₂ O ₃ [#14]	DM
97	Fe-Al (1:2)	Fe(NO ₃) ₃ .9H ₂ O & Al(NO ₃) ₃ .9H ₂ O	DEP
98	Fe-Al (1:2)	Fe ₂ O ₃ [#59] & Al ₂ O ₃ [#14]	DM
99	Fe-Cu-Al (0.5:0.5:1)	Fe(NO ₃) ₃ .9H ₂ O, Cu(NO ₃) ₂ .2.5H ₂ O & Al(NO ₃) ₃ .9H ₂ O	DP
100	Fe-Cu-Al (0.5:0.5:1)	Fe ₂ O ₃ [#59], CuO [#57] & Al ₂ O ₃ [#14]	DM
101	Fe-Cu-Al (0.5:1:1)	Fe(NO ₃) ₃ .9H ₂ O, Cu(NO ₃) ₂ .2.5H ₂ O & Al(NO ₃) ₃ .9H ₂ O	DP
102	Fe-Cu-Al (0.5:1:1)	Fe ₂ O ₃ [#59], CuO [#57] & Al ₂ O ₃ [#14]	DM
103	Fe-Cu-Al (1:1:1)	Fe(NO ₃) ₃ .9H ₂ O, Cu(NO ₃) ₂ .2.5H ₂ O & Al(NO ₃) ₃ .9H ₂ O	DP
104	Fe-Cu-Al (1:1:1)	Fe ₂ O ₃ [#59], CuO [#57] & Al ₂ O ₃ [#14]	DM
105	Fe-Cu-Al (1:1:0.5)	Fe(NO ₃) ₃ .9H ₂ O, Cu(NO ₃) ₂ .2.5H ₂ O & Al(NO ₃) ₃ .9H ₂ O	DP
106	Fe-Cu-Al (1:1:0.5)	Fe ₂ O ₃ [#59], CuO [#57] & Al ₂ O ₃ [#14]	DM

Figure 22: X-Ray diffractograms of synthesized Fe-Cu oxides – DP method.

Figure 23: X-Ray diffractograms of synthesized Cu-Al oxides – DP method.

Figure 24: X-Ray diffractograms of synthesized Fe-Al oxides – DP method.

Figure 25: X-Ray diffractograms of synthesized Fe-Cu-Al oxides – DP method.

Figure 26: SEM micrographs of mixed oxides (ratio 1:1) (a) Fe-Cu [#87], (b) Fe-Al [#95], and Cu-Al [#91].

3.3. Structured materials

Following the preparation procedure already described in Section 2.3, high-temperature (HT) catalytic materials have also been structured in near-spherical samples of 1-2 mm in diameter, all of which were calcined at 1000°C prior to their catalytic evaluation. The calcination temperature has been decided based on past experience and relative literature dictating that when HT catalysts are calcined at temperatures above 1000°C, the calcination temperature has a detrimental effect on their performance. The main target is to reach the optimum compromise between their catalytic performance and their mechanical stability, which for most cases is achieved around 1000°C as due to sintering phenomena, their CS is improved in that zone. Table 16 presents the HT materials that were structured in spherical particles together with their CS in their fresh (calcined) form.

Table 16: Structured materials – Supported single and mixed oxides.

Sample No.	Supported Oxides	Synthesis Method	Crushing Strength (N)
107	CeO ₂ /Kaolinite [#60]	DEP	3
108	CeO ₂ /Kaolinite [#61]	DM	4
109	CeO ₂ /Kaolinite [#62]	DM	5
110	CeO ₂ /SiO ₂ [#63]	DEP	1
111	CeO ₂ /SiO ₂ [#64]	DM	1
112	CeO ₂ /SiO ₂ [#65]	DM	1
113	CeO ₂ /Al ₂ O ₃ [#67]	DM	2
114	CuO/Kaolinite [#69]	DEP	23
115	CuO/Kaolinite [#70]	DM	30
116	CuO/Kaolinite [#71]	DM	28
117	CuO/SiO ₂ [#72]	DEP	5
118	CuO/SiO ₂ [#73]	DM	15

119	CuO/SiO ₂ [#74]	DM	11
120	CuO/Al ₂ O ₃ [#75]	DEP	5
121	CuO/Al ₂ O ₃ [#76]	DM	8
122	CuO/Al ₂ O ₃ [#77]	DM	1
123	Fe ₂ O ₃ /Kaolinite [#78]	DP	3
124	Fe ₂ O ₃ /Kaolinite [#79]	DM	4
125	Fe ₂ O ₃ /Kaolinite [#80]	DM	3
126	Fe ₂ O ₃ /SiO ₂ [#81]	DP	<i>pending</i>
127	Fe ₂ O ₃ /SiO ₂ [#82]	DM	1
128	Fe ₂ O ₃ /SiO ₂ [#83]	DM	<i>pending</i>
129	Fe ₂ O ₃ /Al ₂ O ₃ [#84]	DP	<i>pending</i>
130	Fe ₂ O ₃ /Al ₂ O ₃ [#85]	DM	4
131	Fe ₂ O ₃ /Al ₂ O ₃ [#86]	DM	1

Figure 27 includes indicative photographs of CuO-, Fe₂O₃- and CeO₂-based samples respectively.

Figure 27: Spherical particles of samples (a) CuO/Kaolinite 15/85 wt% [#70], (b) CuO/Kaolinite 15/85 wt% [#71], (c) CuO/SiO₂ 15/85 wt% [#72], (d) CuO/SiO₂ 15/85 wt% [#74], (e) Fe₂O₃/Kaolinite 15/85 wt% [#79], (f) Fe₂O₃/Kaolinite 15/85 wt% [#62]

3.4. Hg-porosimetry of structured catalysts

Freshly calcined catalysts were subjected to Hg-porosimetry measurements in order to identify their porosity as well as their pore size distribution. For brevity, Figure 29 contains the Hg-porosimetry results of three of the best performing samples in terms of their catalytic activity, i.e. CuO/Kaolinite [#71], CuO/SiO₂ [#72], and CuO/SiO₂ [#74] (please refer to the next section for the detailed SO₃ conversion results).

Figure 28: Indicative Hg-porosimetry results for (a) CuO/Kaolinite [#71], (b) CuO/SiO₂ [#72], and (c) CuO/SiO₂ [#74].

The measured porosity of the abovementioned catalysts was 12, 43 and 34% respectively; i.e. the use of SiO₂ as support ensures substantially higher porosity cf. Kaolinite. For the case of CuO/Kaolinite [#71] it is evident that there is porosity (micropores) that is out of the measuring range of the instrument (<0.01 μm), while the majority of the pore size distribution ranges between 0.1 – 1 μm (macropores). Some porosity is also identified at diameters of around 50 μm. The other two samples, supported both on SiO₂, exhibit a very similar pattern, as in both cases the pore size distribution range lies between 0.1 – 1 μm, or closer to 0.5 μm.

4. Catalytic Performance Evaluation

Synthesized materials were and several of them are currently being tested w.r.t. their performance in the STS reaction, in a continuous flow, in-house unit at CERTH. The unit has been designed and constructed to fit the needs of the SAS process in an efficient, and as easy as possible to operate, manner.

4.1. Catalytic evaluation unit

The catalytic evaluation unit at CERTH used for catalytic materials screening (Figure 29 (a) and (b)), consists of a quartz tube serving as a packed bed reactor, an electrically heated furnace, a valveless rotary piston pump feeding the (liquid) concentrated or diluted H₂SO₄ to the inlet of the reactor, two mass flow controllers (MFCs), a cuvette and a UV lamp/UV-Vis spectrometer. The first MFC (up to 10 lpm) is used to dilute the reactor outlet and perform the daily SO₂ calibration and the second (up to 2 lpm) to potentially dilute the H₂SO₄ inlet stream for selected (e.g. V-based) materials testing. All lines downstream the reactor are heated at 185°C in order to avoid extensive formation of condensates during the experimental testing (~ 1 h of reaction per test). The material utilized for the tubing and the tube accessories is PFA/PTFE due to the highly corrosive operating conditions and its thermal stability exceeding 200°C.

The left part of the quartz tube reactor (upstream the catalytic bed) is filled with quartz beads, while downstream the sample the tube is filled with quartz wool (Figure 29 (c) and (d)). Quartz beads ensure homogeneous (i.e. pulse-free) flow of the liquid sulphuric acid and quartz wool effectively supports/immobilizes the catalytic particles while it also contributes to homogenization of the gaseous reactor outlet stream. Thus, instabilities in the SO₂ signal measured at the cuvette by the UV-Vis setup are avoided. The samples are placed in a fixed bed configuration in the middle section of the quartz tube. The SO₂ analysis takes place using a UV lamp and a UV-Vis spectrometer in a heated (~212°C) quartz cuvette. A daily SO₂ calibration (using 0.5, 1.0 and 1.5% SO₂ bottles respectively) ensures measurement accuracy. Additionally, the reactor outlet is diluted with a controlled nitrogen flow (0.5 - 3 std lt/min) to decrease the concentration of SO₂ at the reactor outlet to levels within the calibration range of the UV-Vis setup. After completion of each experiment, all remaining liquid sulphuric acid upstream the reactor is pumped back to the sulphuric acid container and the bed is cooled down to approximately 500°C with no flow. From that point and down to about 400°C, N₂ flow is applied to purge the system from residual sulphuric species and clean the piping before and after the reactor. Figure 29 includes a schematic and a photographic depiction of the test rig assembled by CERTH, with all major components as described above. Table 17 includes the experimental conditions applied for the preliminary tests depending on whether the catalyst is used for medium or high temperature STS. The parameters, especially for MT catalysts, are subject to changes as the nature of V-based materials is highly challenging, with the main target being to reduce the gas hourly space velocity (GHSV) of the reaction in order to lie within the thermodynamic ranges of the MT reaction.

Table 17: Experimental conditions depending on the catalyst type

Parameters	Medium-temperature (MT) catalysts	High-temperature (HT) catalysts
Reaction temperature (°C)	650	850
Pressure (bar)	1	1
H ₂ SO ₄ feed conc. (%)	25	95-98 (96.5)
H ₂ SO ₄ feed rate (ml/min)	0.12	0.12
Mole fraction, x _{SO₃} (-)	0.125	0.500
GHSV (h ⁻¹)	7,700	11,800
WHSV (h ⁻¹)	8.5	13.2
Catalyst quantity (g)	1	1
On-stream exposure (min)	60	60

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 29: Catalytic evaluation unit at CERTH: (a), (b) overview, and (c), (d) indicative photographs of the loaded reactor.

4.2. Catalytic performance results

4.2.1. High-temperature (HT) catalysts

Selected HT catalytic materials that have so far been tested in the catalytic unit, along with their results, are summarized in Table 18, providing also information w.r.t. their particle color, absolute SO₃ conversion and CS before and after the 1 h on-stream exposure. The SO₃ conversion values corresponding to the gas phase/"blank" is measured at 2.2%, while the thermodynamic conversion considering 50% SO₃ / 50% H₂O feed was calculated at 81%. The SO₃ conversion target set in the Project is 75% of the thermodynamic conversion, meaning that the absolute SO₃ conversion threshold is set at ≥ 60% for the case of the HT catalysts. The most promising samples, i.e. combining optimum overall combination of catalytic activity and fresh/used CS values, are highlighted in green. Currently, the experimental campaign on MT, V₂O₅-based catalysts is underway following the experimental conditions shown above.

Table 18: Results of preliminary catalytic activity tests.

Sample name	Color (used)	SO ₃ conversion (%)	Crushing Strength (N)	
			fresh	used
Fe ₂ O ₃ [#59]	dark red/blackish	42	21	30
Fe ₂ O ₃ /Kaolinite [#79]	dark red/blackish	23	4	12
Fe ₂ O ₃ /SiO ₂ [#82]	dark red/blackish	37	1	5
Fe ₂ O ₃ /Al ₂ O ₃ [#85]	dark red/blackish	23	4	12
Fe ₂ O ₃ /Kaolinite [#78]	dark red/blackish	32	3	5
CuO/Kaolinite [#70]	dark grey/brown	60	30	31
CuO/Kaolinite [#71]	dark grey/brown	59	28	21
CuO/Kaolinite [#69]	dark grey/brown	52	23	31
CuO/Al ₂ O ₃ [#76]	dark grey/reddish brown	35	8	21
CuO/SiO ₂ [#73]	dark grey	37	15	21
CuO/SiO₂ [#74]	dark grey	60	11	5
CuO/SiO₂ [#72]	dark grey	67	5	7
CeO ₂ /Kaolinite [#62]	pink	12	5	12
CeO ₂ /Kaolinite [#60]	pink	40	3	12
BiVO ₄ /Kaolinite [#30]	yellow	25	3	14
BiVO ₄ (powder form)	yellow	34	-	-

Based on the preliminary results, four samples have already shown an SO₃ conversion in the range of 75% of the corresponding thermodynamic value (calculated at 81%), while at the same time exhibited satisfactory thermomechanical stability. All these samples are in-principle qualified compositions for the long-term tests that will be carried out by DLR in the following months. Naturally, the list will be enriched with additional materials that will also include V₂O₅-based compositions.

For comparative reasons, the following Figures (Figure 30 - Figure 33) are grouped based on the main active oxide presenting both SO₃ conversion and CS results of the materials before (fresh) and after the 1 h exposure experiment (used).

Figure 30: SO₃ conversion and measured CS values for Fe-based particles calcined at 1000°C supported [#85, #82, #79, #78] and 950°C unsupported [#59]; where mixed Fe₂O₃/support = 15/85 wt%.

Figure 31: SO₃ conversion and measured CS values for Cu-based particles calcined at 1000°C; where mixed CuO/kaolinite = 15/85 wt%.

Figure 32: SO₃ conversion and measured CS values for Cu-based particles calcined at 1000°C; where mixed CuO/support = 15/85 wt%.

It is evident from the relative results that CuO formulations supported on kaolinite or SiO₂ have significantly higher performance than the Fe₂O₃-based materials. As already stressed out, the most promising samples, in-principle qualified for further testing at DLR's setup are CuO/Kaolinite [#70], CuO/Kaolinite [#71], CuO/SiO₂ [#72], CuO/SiO₂ [#74] with the SO₃ conversion very close or above 60% which is very close to the target of 75% of the corresponding thermodynamic value. The active catalysts of the most promising compositions were synthesized in-lab (#71, #72 and #74 using the DEP method) or commercially acquired (as in #70) followed by direct dry mixing of the catalytically active oxide and the substrates (kaolinite and SiO₂) except for the case of #72, where DEP method was also employed for the mixing of the catalyst with SiO₂.

Figure 33: SO₃ conversion and measured CS values for CeO₂-based particles calcined at 1000°C [#60, #62] and BiVO₄ based particles calcined at 700°C [#30]; where mixed CeO₂/kaolinite and BiVO₄/kaolinite = 15/85 wt%.

It is noteworthy that when CeO₂ was employed as a high temperature catalyst, it underperformed. In addition, BiVO₄, due to its high melting point (880-940°C) was tested as a high temperature catalyst, but underperformed as well, with a medium to low SO₃ conversion

(up to 35% or 43% of the thermodynamic value depending on the formulation). As a result, it will be further tested as a MT catalyst.

The following Figure 34 shows indicative photographs of Fe₂O₃-based particles (Figure 34 a., b.) and CuO-based particles (Figure 34 c., d.), before and after the preliminary, 1-hour experiment. It is evident that in the case of the Cu-based materials, a slight decoloring of the sample takes place. The decoloring is attributed to a thin layer of (dark colored) CuO on the surface of the particle surrounding the catalytically active phase (CuAl₂O₄), which is absent from the used sample.

Figure 34: Photographs of [a.,b.] Fe₂O₃-based [#79.] and [c.,d.] CuO-based [#70] particles before and after testing respectively

4.2.2. Medium-temperature (MT) catalysts

Regarding the MT, V-based catalysts, due to the more challenging nature of the reaction conditions and associated thermodynamic limitations, the experimental campaign is currently underway considering also some modifications of employed conditions, especially in terms of the definition of the reaction parameters, mainly by reducing the GHSV of the reaction to compensate for potential slow reaction rates due to substantially lower reaction temperature. The thermodynamic SO₃ conversion at 650°C with the relatively dilute 25% H₂SO₄ is 53% as calculated using appropriate simulation tools (HSC Chemistry™ Software). Table 19 includes indicative results of three V-based catalysts assessed so far, all of which supported on kaolinite at a ratio of catalyst/support = 15/85 wt%. More specifically, sample #5 comprises a commercial V₂O₅ grade supported on kaolinite with DEP, whereas #6 and #7 consist of a commercial and thermally treated V₂O₅ grade respectively, supported on kaolinite with DM. It is also noted that the “blank” (i.e. no catalyst) SO₃ conversion at the MT conditions employed so far is not measurable (i.e. < 1%).

Table 19: Results of preliminary catalytic activity tests.

Sample name	SO ₃ conversion (%)	Crushing Strength (N)	
		fresh	used
V ₂ O ₅ /Kaolinite [#5]	5	3	11
V ₂ O ₅ /Kaolinite [#6]	7	9	11
V ₂ O ₅ /Kaolinite [#7]	7	7	10

As shown in the results, the SO₃ conversion measured with the initially set parameters, as presented in Table 17, is significantly low. Some V-leaching is observed in all cases, especially since the support (e.g. kaolinite) content is only 15 wt%. On the other hand, the CS in all cases improves after the experiment, which is a positive sign in terms of their thermomechanical stability. BiVO₄, which has so far been tested as a HT catalyst, will be also studied as a MT catalyst thanks to its promising properties, including its low or no toxicity, especially when compared to the other, V-based oxides. Further MT catalysts testing as well as parameters fine tuning is currently underway.

4.3. Physicochemical characterization of used samples

Currently, the physicochemical characterization of the used samples is underway, including XRD, SEM/EDS and TGA of the most active catalytic formulations identified so far, with the aim to also compare them to the corresponding fresh ones.

As widely adopted in the relevant literature, the general reaction mechanism of the STS reaction is $\text{SO}_{3(\text{g})} + \text{MO}_{(\text{s})} \rightarrow \text{MSO}_{4(\text{s})}$; $\text{MSO}_{4(\text{s})} \rightarrow \text{SO}_{2(\text{g})} + \frac{1}{2} \text{O}_{2(\text{g})} + \text{MO}_{(\text{s})}$. The aforementioned physico-chemical methods will provide qualitative and quantitative estimation of the sulphated species content of the used catalytic compositions, which is an important validation metric of the catalytic evaluation results. Based on the carefully defined experiments' cooling protocol followed (see details earlier in this Section), the metal sulphate content can be interpreted as a strong indication for appreciable SO₃ conversion. All main physicochemical characterizations of used samples will be provided in the upcoming periodic technical report of RP1.

5. Conclusions

The current Deliverable contains the physicochemical characterization results of all so far synthesized and shaped materials (>100 different compositions) as well as the preliminarily catalytically evaluated materials (>50 different compositions so far, mainly HT catalysts) at CERTH's in-house purpose-built test rig. In most of the cases, both in MT and HT catalysts, the CS was improved after testing which is largely attributed to further sintering during on-stream exposure.

Among all the so far tested HT samples, four have already exhibited in-principle promising results in terms of both SO₃ conversion and thermomechanical stability, which already is an encouraging step close to the target of Task 3.1. The compositions that are already qualified for further testing at DLR's long-term testing setup are CuO/Kaolinite [#70], CuO/Kaolinite [#71], CuO/SiO₂ [#72], CuO/SiO₂ [#74] with the SO₃ conversion close to the SO1 target of 75% of the corresponding thermodynamic value. The active catalysts of these compositions were either synthesized in-lab (#71, #72 and #74 using the DEP method) or commercially acquired (as in #70) followed by direct dry mixing of the catalytically active oxide and the support materials (kaolinite and SiO₂) except for the case of #72, where DEP method was also employed for the mixing of the active catalyst with the support material. Although CeO₂ was added in the test matrix as an additional candidate HT catalyst, it underperformed and was disqualified from further testing. Fe₂O₃-based catalysts lied in the range of an SO₃ conversion of 50-55% of the corresponding thermodynamic value, which is close but still lower than the 75% threshold. Further investigation of other commercial Fe₂O₃ sources will enable the partners to draw safe conclusions in terms of its qualification. One of the main conclusions drawn by the preliminary evaluation results is that catalysts with a high SO₃ conversion (i.e. close to 75% of the thermodynamic value) are characterized by the presence of measurable macroporosity values (most porosity is observed in the range between 0.1-1 μm) and strong presence of catalytically active phases. CuAl₂O₄ mixed spinel phase showed substantial catalytic activity, while at the same time the mechanical stability, as measured by CS, of the materials is largely attributed to the formation of mixed Al-Si phases as well as to the Al₂O₃ and SiO₂ phases identified by the respective XRD results. All samples exhibited very low surface area values due to their high calcination temperature, which is deemed necessary to provide improved mechanical strength and to comply with the targeted reaction temperatures. The presence of macropores in the case of the CuO-based catalysts, as identified by Hg-porosimetry results, essentially explains the superior catalytic activity over the Fe₂O₃- and CeO₂- rich ones due to the improved solid material-reacting gas contact.

Regarding MT, V-based catalysts, there are so far some challenges observed in terms of the measured SO₃ conversion (currently up to only 13% of the thermodynamic value), while in all cases their CS is improved after their on-stream exposure ensuring satisfactory thermomechanical stability. As the experimental campaign is currently underway, these challenges is foreseen to be tackled with the, currently ongoing, tuning of the testing parameters, however, as reaction parameters modifications are time-consuming and require alterations of the experimental setup, there is currently some minor deviation from the work plan that is planned to be mitigated in the coming months, and especially in view of the RP1 periodic technical report and the upcoming mid-term review meeting.

Within the next few months, long-term experiments at DLR's dedicated test rig will be initiated in order to meet the quantitative targets of the relative SO and Milestone, with the aim to primarily verify the long-term catalytic stability of the in-principle qualified catalysts. Initial long-term test at DLR will involve the 4 shortlisted samples identified herein.

6. References

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